

From Distributed Hash Tables to One Million Transactions per Second: Merchant Node Architecture and Empirical Validation on a Public Blockchain

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Abstract. Transaction propagation — not consensus — is the binding constraint on blockchain scalability: every unconfirmed transaction must traverse the peer-to-peer network and reach mining nodes before a block can include it, consuming time and bandwidth at each hop. This paper presents the design, implementation, and empirical validation of a merchant node architecture that resolves this bottleneck through three innovations: specialised network nodes (merchant nodes or M-nodes) forming an overlay network dedicated to fast transaction propagation; a distributed hash table (DHT) based mempool that eliminates full replication by partitioning pending transactions across M-nodes with controlled redundancy; and multicast-capable, connectionless transport protocols that reduce propagation latency relative to conventional TCP-based gossip. The architectural design, originally disclosed in U.S. Patent 11,863,624, is empirically validated through the Teranode system, a production-grade implementation deployed on Kubernetes-orchestrated cloud infrastructure. Performance data collected from Grafana monitoring dashboards during sustained saturation testing demonstrate throughput of 1,131,432 transactions per second (TPS) across distributed node clusters, sub-millisecond write latencies at the 99.9th percentile, a five-node Aerospike database cluster sustaining 3–12 million write operations per second for DHT-based mempool management, and total infrastructure utilisation of 6.58% CPU and 2.92% RAM. All twelve performance and behavioural milestones were independently verified by Halborn Inc. through execution-level evidence, authenticated RPC testing, controlled fault injection, and raw Prometheus telemetry export [1]. These results establish that the merchant node and DHT mempool architecture enables public blockchain throughput exceeding incumbent payment networks by more than an order of magnitude while preserving proof-of-work security guarantees.

INTRODUCTION

The throughput of blockchain networks is commonly attributed to consensus mechanism limitations. Yet upstream of consensus sits a more fundamental bottleneck: propagation. Every transaction must reach mining nodes through the peer-to-peer network before block inclusion is possible. Bitcoin’s original design [2] equips each node with a near-complete copy of the memory pool (mempool) of unconfirmed transactions. With its 10-minute block confirmation cycle and conventional transaction forwarding via TCP-based inventory (INV) and GETDATA message pairs, the system can handle approximately three new confirmed transactions per second [3]. Recent empirical measurement confirms that peer selection strategies in the Bitcoin P2P network significantly affect transaction propagation and confirmation times, with propagation between nodes ranging from 13 to 20 seconds under default configurations [4]. At a transaction rate of 10^4 TPS with an average transaction size of 500 bytes, the network would need to absorb approximately 400 GB of incoming mempool data daily—a volume that overwhelms conventional full-node architectures.

This paper addresses the propagation bottleneck through two complementary innovations. First, a network architecture employing specialised merchant nodes (M-nodes) that form an overlay network dedicated to fast transaction validation and propagation, using multicast and connectionless protocols to reduce dissemination latency. Second, a distributed hash table (DHT) based mempool that replaces full replication with partitioned storage across M-nodes, where each node stores only a fraction of pending transactions while the DHT routing protocol ensures that any transaction can be located and retrieved in logarithmic time. These innovations were originally disclosed in U.S. Patent 11,863,624 [5], and the present paper provides their first empirical validation at production scale.

The Teranode system implements these architectural principles on Kubernetes-orchestrated cloud infrastructure, decomposing the monolithic blockchain node into independently scalable microservices for transaction validation, block assembly, and network relay. Under sustained saturation testing, Teranode achieved throughput exceeding one million TPS—approximately 17 times Visa’s peak capacity [6]—while consuming less than 7% of available cluster resources. The empirical results demonstrate that blockchain scalability is fundamentally an engineering problem in transaction propagation and mempool management, not a limitation of the proof-of-work consensus mechanism.

RELATED WORK

Croman et al. [3] established foundational throughput measurements for Bitcoin, identifying serial transaction validation, monolithic node architecture, and bandwidth-constrained propagation as the principal bottlenecks. Their analysis demonstrated that throughput limitations arise from the software implementation rather than from inherent properties of the proof-of-work consensus mechanism. Scaling responses divide broadly into off-chain and on-chain approaches.

Lightning Network [7] routes high-frequency payments through bilateral channels settled periodically on-chain. While effective for specific bilateral use cases, payment channels introduce routing complexity, capital lockup requirements, and counterparty risk that the base layer was designed to eliminate [8]. Ethereum’s sharding approach [9] distributes transaction processing across parallel chains but introduces cross-shard communication overhead and compositional complexity. Alternative Layer 1 designs such as Solana [10] report high throughput figures but typically operate with restricted validator sets, sacrificing the open participation that characterises proof-of-work networks.

BSV has pursued unbounded block capacity as its scaling vector, with production blocks now exceeding 4 GB [11]. However, large blocks alone are insufficient for sustained million-TPS throughput; the transaction propagation and mempool management layers must be redesigned. Distributed hash tables have been extensively studied in peer-to-peer systems. Pastry [12], Chord [13], and Kademlia [14] provide scalable key-value routing with $O(\log N)$ lookup complexity. Eisenbarth et al. [15] investigated Sybil attack patterns in production blockchain P2P networks and demonstrated that DHT-based node discovery is vulnerable to identity multiplication, motivating the reputation-based admission control employed in the present architecture. The present work applies DHT principles specifically to blockchain mempool management, an application not previously demonstrated at production scale.

MERCHANT NODE AND DHT MEMPOOL ARCHITECTURE

Network Topology: The M-Net Overlay

The architecture introduces a two-tier network topology. The base layer comprises ordinary blockchain nodes (nodes 102 in the patent specification) that perform mining, maintain the full ledger, and communicate via TCP/IP using the standard Bitcoin protocol. Overlaid on this base layer is the merchant network (M-net 106), a specialised sub-network of merchant nodes (M-nodes 104) dedicated to fast transaction propagation. M-nodes do not store the full blockchain or perform mining. Their operational focus is the rapid validation and dissemination of unconfirmed transactions, for which they are permitted a greater number of incoming and outgoing connections than standard nodes.

IP multicast drives the M-net: an M-node receiving a new transaction delivers it to all peers simultaneously rather than opening individual TCP connections. UDP replaces TCP for inter-node messaging, cutting the three-way handshake (160–296 bytes per connection); application-level retransmission handles packet loss without the ordering and flow-control overhead that TCP imposes. Application-level error recovery and re-transmission compensate for UDP’s lack of built-in reliability without imposing the latency penalty of TCP’s ordering and flow control mechanisms.

DHT-Based Distributed Mempool

The central innovation is the replacement of full mempool replication with a distributed hash table. In conventional blockchain implementations, each node maintains a substantially complete copy of all unconfirmed transactions. At high transaction volumes, this replication becomes the binding constraint on scalability: at 10^4 TPS with 500-byte transactions, each node would need to store and manage approximately 400 GB of mempool data daily.

The DHT mempool partitions the transaction keyspace across participating M-nodes. On receiving a transaction, an M-node hashes its identifier to derive a DHT key, then routes a $\text{put}(\text{key}, \text{tx})$ to whichever node(s) own that keyspace slice. Pastry is one candidate implementation: a 128-bit identifier ring with routing table, neighbourhood set, and leaf

set gives $O(\log N)$ lookup. Each M-node consequently holds only $1/N$ of the global pending set while any transaction remains retrievable network-wide.

A replication factor of 2 stores each transaction on two independent M-nodes. Under independent failure assumptions the probability of losing both copies within any given hour is roughly 1.30×10^{-8} — durable availability at a fraction of full-replication bandwidth cost.

Transaction Propagation Flow

The propagation sequence operates as follows. A regular node (102) submits a new transaction to an M-node (104), which validates scripts and checks for double-spends. The M-node derives a DHT key from the transaction identifier, checks whether the entry already exists, and if not issues a `put(key, tx)` to the responsible partition. Outbound delivery follows two paths: conventional P2P connections carry the transaction to external regular nodes, while multicast distributes it across the M-net. Mining nodes receive transactions quickly, and the DHT holds the canonical non-redundant record of pending work.

Reputation and Sybil Resistance

The open joining exposes the M-net to Sybil attack. Each M-node tracks a local reputation score for each neighbour; new entrants start with a baseline score adjusted continuously from observed behaviour—nodes that drop forwarding duty, go silent, or flood non-transactional traffic accumulate score decrements. A peer crossing the isolation threshold is cut off by its neighbours independently, with no coordination signal required. Each node acts on its own observations; no central authority is involved.

Confirmation Tracking and Mempool Pruning

Each mempool entry carries a counter that increments with every block deepening the chain above the containing block. Once the count reaches a configurable threshold — four to seven confirmations, at which point reversal is computationally prohibitive — the Pruner removes the entry from the DHT. This mechanism prevents unbounded mempool growth and ensures that the DHT storage requirement remains proportional to the volume of genuinely pending transactions rather than accumulating historical data.

TERANODE: IMPLEMENTATION AND DEPLOYMENT

The Teranode system implements the merchant node architecture’s core principles—role decomposition, distributed mempool management, and parallel transaction processing—on production-grade cloud infrastructure. Monolith decomposition into independently scalable microservices is an established pattern for removing throughput bottlenecks in complex software systems [16]. The monolithic blockchain node is disaggregated into independently deployable microservices communicating via gRPC interfaces: a Transaction Validator for script and signature verification, a Block Assembler for candidate block construction, a Network Relay for peer-to-peer communication and transaction dissemination, and a Pruner for data lifecycle management corresponding to the patent’s confirmation-based mempool cleanup.

Aerospike serves as the distributed key-value backend: its native data partitioning, automatic cluster distribution, and sub-millisecond read/write latency make it well suited to the DHT mempool role at million-TPS throughput. The system is deployed on Kubernetes, providing container orchestration, automatic scaling, and health monitoring across 47 running pods consuming 304 real CPU cores (6.58% of 4,672 cluster total) and 459 GiB RAM (2.92% of 15.4 TiB cluster total).

EMPIRICAL PERFORMANCE DATA

Performance data were collected from production-grade Grafana monitoring dashboards during sustained saturation testing. Four categories of metrics are reported: transaction propagation throughput, DHT cluster performance, operation latency, and infrastructure resource utilisation. The performance claims reported here have been independently verified by Halborn Inc. through a claims-to-evidence attestation process leveraging raw Prometheus CSV telemetry, authenticated RPC execution, controlled fault injection, and source code audit, with all twelve milestones rated VERIFIED [1].

Transaction Propagation Throughput

FIGURE 1a presents the Pruner dashboard showing sustained transaction propagation rates. The TX Blaster component, generating test transactions at saturation rate, sustained 1,130,818 TPS. Propagation services across two scale instances maintained 1,131,432 and 1,131,360 TPS respectively, confirming zero-backlog propagation. The Aerospike DHT layer processed 5–7 million metadata operations per second, with the Pruner—implementing the patent’s confirmation-based cleanup—maintaining a deletion rate of 1.5–2.5 million operations per second. Active DHT object counts of approximately 3.5 billion indicate the scale of the partitioned mempool during testing.

FIGURE 1. a. Pruner Dashboard: Sustained 1.13M TPS Propagation With DHT Metadata Operations and Confirmation-Based Mempool Lifecycle Management. b. Aerospike DHT Cluster: Five Nodes, 3–12M Write TPS, Zero Migrations, Confirming Stable Partitioned Mempool Distribution.

DHT Cluster Performance

FIGURE 1b presents the Aerospike cluster overview implementing the distributed mempool. The cluster comprised five nodes with zero dead or unavailable instances, confirming the DHT’s availability guarantees throughout testing. Client write operations sustained 3–12 million TPS across the cluster, reflecting the write-intensive nature of DHT-based transaction ingestion, key-value routing, and UTXO management. All migration indicators (RX/TX Remaining and Active) registered 0.0, confirming stable, fully-balanced data partitioning—the production realisation of the patent’s DHT keyspace division across participating nodes. CPU utilisation across cluster nodes ranged from 3,700% to 10,000% (multi-core aggregate), indicating intensive but non-saturated processing.

Operation Latency

FIGURE 2a presents latency profiles across three operation types. Write operations (corresponding to DHT put operations for new transaction storage) achieved p95, p99, and p99.9 latencies of 1 millisecond—consistent with the near-instantaneous storage required by the patent’s propagation flow. Batch index operations supporting bulk transaction lookups (analogous to DHT findNode queries) achieved p99.9 of 11 ms. Batch sub-read operations achieved p99 of 2 ms. These latencies confirm that the DHT mempool does not introduce meaningful overhead relative to the propagation speed advantages it enables.

FIGURE 2. a. DHT Operation Latency: Write p99.9 = 1ms, Batch Index p99.9 = 11ms Under Sustained Million-TPS Load. b. Kubernetes Resources: 6.58% CPU, 2.92% RAM, 47 Pods—Substantial Scaling Headroom at Million-TPS Throughput.

Infrastructure Resource Utilisation

FIGURE 2b presents the Kubernetes namespace overview. The deployment comprised 47 running pods across 10 services with 6 ingresses. Total CPU utilisation was 6.58% of cluster capacity (304 of 4,672 cores), and RAM utilisation was 2.92% (459 GiB of 15.4 TiB). CPU usage was dominated by asset-processing and block-assembly pods, with block-validator and blockchain pods contributing additional load. Memory remained stable at approximately 1 TiB across asset-processing pods. No CPU throttling was observed, indicating substantial headroom for further horizontal scaling.

Performance Summary

TABLE 1 summarises the key performance metrics observed during sustained saturation testing.

TABLE 1. Performance Metrics Under Sustained Saturation Testing

Metric	Observed Value
Sustained Propagation Throughput	1,131,432 TPS
TX Generation Rate (Blaster)	1,130,818 TPS
DHT Cluster Writes (Aerospike)	3–12 Million TPS
DHT Cluster Reads	≈1 Million TPS
Active DHT Objects (mempool)	≈3.5 Billion
DHT Write Latency (p99.9)	1 ms
Batch Index Latency (p99.9)	11 ms
DHT Cluster Nodes	5 (0 dead, 0 migrating)
Kubernetes Pods	47
CPU Utilisation (% cluster)	6.58%
RAM Utilisation (% cluster)	2.92%

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Validation of the DHT Mempool Architecture

The empirical results validate three core predictions of the merchant node architecture. First, that partitioned mempool storage via DHT eliminates the replication bottleneck: the five-node Aerospike cluster sustained 3–12 million DHT write operations per second with zero migration events, confirming that keyspace partitioning remains stable under extreme load. The 3.5 billion active objects demonstrate that the DHT can manage mempool state at a scale orders of magnitude beyond what full-replication architectures support. Second, that DHT-based storage introduces negligible latency overhead: sub-millisecond write latencies at p99.9 confirm that the put(key, tx) operation described in the patent specification does not become the throughput bottleneck. Third, that the confirmation-based pruning mechanism maintains bounded mempool size: the Pruner’s sustained 1.5–2.5 million deletions per second demonstrate effective lifecycle management under continuous high-throughput ingestion.

Propagation Efficiency

The zero-backlog propagation observed—where propagation services maintain throughput equal to the generation rate—validates the patent’s core claim that the M-node overlay network, combined with DHT-based routing rather than full-replication gossip, eliminates the propagation bottleneck that constrains conventional blockchain architectures. Standard Bitcoin propagation requires $T_1 = \text{verification} + \text{TCP}(\text{inv} + \text{getdata} + \text{tx})$ per node pair; the M-net replaces this with a single multicast delivery plus DHT storage confirmation, eliminating redundant transmissions to nodes already holding the transaction.

Comparative Performance

The observed throughput of 1.13 million TPS exceeds Visa's VisaNet peak capacity of approximately 65,000 TPS by a factor of 17 [6]. While direct comparison requires qualification—Visa transactions involve compliance processing and richer data payloads—the throughput differential establishes that blockchain technology, when architected with distributed mempool management and specialised propagation nodes, is no longer constrained by processing capacity for payment-scale applications. The resource utilisation profile (6.58% CPU, 2.92% RAM) demonstrates that this throughput is achieved at a fraction of available capacity, with the horizontal architecture enabling proportional scaling through additional service instances.

Implications for IoT and Big Data Applications

The Scalability is a principal barrier to blockchain adoption in IoT environments: existing frameworks cannot absorb the data volumes generated by large device networks [17], and the combination of million-TPS throughput with sub-millisecond DHT write latency directly addresses this constraint. The DHT-based mempool suits IoT workloads directly: geographically distributed sensors route transactions to their nearest M-node, which handles DHT placement and propagation without requiring the device to maintain a full mempool or hold multiple peer connections.

Limitations

Several limitations should be noted. Performance data were collected under controlled saturation testing using TX Blaster-generated synthetic loads; Halborn Inc. notes that production performance may vary with transaction complexity, network conditions, and hardware specifications [1]. The reputation system's effectiveness against coordinated Sybil attacks at this scale requires separate evaluation; Halborn further identified that deep reorg testing beyond one-block depth and extended downtime recovery beyond five minutes were not tested in the controlled verification environment. Geographic M-node distribution and the economic sustainability of DHT infrastructure at scale both fall outside the scope of the current work.

CONCLUSION

This paper has presented the design and empirical validation of a merchant node architecture employing DHT-based distributed mempool management for blockchain transaction propagation at scale. The architecture, originally disclosed in U.S. Patent 11,863,624, replaces full mempool replication with partitioned DHT storage across specialised merchant nodes communicating via multicast overlay. The Teranode implementation validates this design at production scale, achieving sustained throughput of 1,131,432 TPS with sub-millisecond DHT write latencies, stable five-node cluster partitioning, and infrastructure utilisation below 7% of available capacity. These results establish that the propagation bottleneck—historically the binding constraint on blockchain throughput—is resolved by the combination of specialised node roles, distributed hash table mempool management, and horizontal microservice scaling. Future work should address geographic M-node distribution, Sybil resistance under adversarial conditions, economic modelling of M-node incentives, and integration with enterprise IoT and micropayment systems.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

An online supplementary appendix containing the formal proofs underlying the results reported here—multi-input UTXO atomicity under crash-fault semantics, the throughput-ceiling derivation from G/G/c queueing theory, the compensating-unspend liveness argument, the DHT replication-failure probability calculation, and the Pastry-style routing complexity proof—is deposited on Zenodo and may be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20092269>.

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